

Consumption (%)

2. Bait consumption during a long-term baiting test at the IRRI Rice Genetic Resources Laboratory, 1981.

attained by baiting all possible breeding areas (Fig. 2).

Mice in the storage rooms fed on pelletized baits despite the abundance of

rice, showing the attractiveness of the bait. ■

Irrigation and water management

Water management in dry season rice

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Dry season rice in West Bengal requires large quantities (170-180 cm) of water, 50-60% of which is lost in deep percolation because of continuous deep submergence of fields. Water requirements can be reduced. The medium-duration (120 days) rice cultivar IET 2815 was grown on clay loam with 8 water management practices (see table). Yields were higher with 10-0 cm water from transplanting to yellow ripe stage than with 5-0 cm. Irrigating the crop 2 days after complete recession of 10-cm standing water did not reduce grain yield from that obtained by irrigating sooner, but the irrigation requirement was

Influence of 8 water management practices on grain yield and irrigation requirement of dry season rice in West Bengal.

Water management practice	Grain yield (t/ha)			Av irrigation requirement ^a (cm)
	1977-78	1978-79	Av	
10-0 cm water regime from transplanting to yellow ripe stage	3.8	5.0	4.4	180 (18)
5-0 cm water regime from transplanting to yellow ripe stage	3.6	4.1	3.8	100 (20)
Stress ^b during early tillering, no stress ^c during rest	3.4	4.3	3.8	90 (18)
Stress during late tillering, no stress during rest	3.7	4.3	4.0	90 (18)
Stress during flowering, no stress during rest	3.6	4.0	3.8	90 (18)
Stress during grain filling, no stress during rest	3.8	4.7	4.2	90 (18)
10 cm irrigation 2 days after recession of standing water, from transplanting to yellow ripe stage	3.9	5.1	4.5	140 (14)
5 cm irrigation 2 days after recession of standing water, from transplanting to yellow ripe stage	3.8	4.8	4.3	80 (16)
C.D. (5%)	0.24	0.15		

^aThe figures in parentheses denote number of irrigations. ^bStress: application of 5 cm water 2 days after recession to 0 cm. ^cNo stress: application of 5 cm water immediately after recession to 0 cm.

reduced by 20-22%. The flowering stage was found most sensitive and the grain-

filling stage least sensitive to water stress. ■